

FACTORS MODIFYING THE DEVELOPMENT OF CARDIOTOXIC COMPLICATIONS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF ANTHRACYCLINE CHEMOTHERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE LEUKEMIA

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ABSTRACT

Cardiotoxic complications against the background of anthracycline chemotherapy are an important clinical problem that limits the effectiveness of treatment of patients with acute leukemia. Oxidative stress, which leads to cardiomyocyte damage, impaired contractile function, and the development of electrical instability, is considered one of the key mechanisms of cardiotoxic damage. In recent years, particular attention has been paid to ferroptosis, an iron-dependent form of regulated cell death caused by the accumulation of lipid peroxidation products.

Relevance. Cardiotoxic complications against the background of anthracycline chemotherapy are an important clinical problem that limits the effectiveness of treatment of patients with acute leukemia. Oxidative stress, which leads to cardiomyocyte damage, impaired contractile function, and the development of electrical instability, is considered one of the key mechanisms of cardiotoxic damage. In recent years, particular attention has been paid to ferroptosis, an iron-dependent form of regulated cell death caused by the accumulation of lipid peroxidation products.

Individual differences in cardiotoxicity indicate the importance of molecular-genetic factors associated with oxidative stress and the antioxidant defense system.

Research objective. To assess the role of molecular-genetic factors in the formation of cardiotoxic complications against the background of anthracycline chemotherapy in patients with acute leukemia.

Materials and methods. A total of 87 patients with acute leukemia were included in the study, of which 63 had acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) and 24 had acute myeloblastic leukemia (AML). All patients were treated with standard chemotherapy regimens including anthracyclines. Cardiotoxicity was assessed dynamically based on clinical and echocardiographic parameters.

Results. Cardiotoxic complications were manifested by impaired myocardial function and early subclinical changes in some patients. The observed changes indicate the possible role of molecular-genetic factors in the development of cardiotoxicity.

Conclusion. Molecular-genetic factors are important in the formation of cardiotoxic complications that develop against the background of anthracycline chemotherapy. Taking them into account will serve to stratify cardiovascular risk and improve individual monitoring strategies.

